

The Role of Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel in Integration of Hyderabad State into Indian Union – A Study

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Abstract:

Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel was a great freedom fighter. He organized several movements under Gandhiji leadership. Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel made significant contribution for united India. His stern discipline, timeline strategies, Iron will and diplomacy made 562 Princely States into one Nation. Among these Patel's role in integration of Hyderabad State was one of the unique episode. Several historical events rushed in making Hyderabad integration in complex environment.

Key Words: Integration, Princely States, Strategies

Introduction:

As observed by Gurumukh Nihal Singh "Nature has made India a more or less self-sufficient unit, but historical accidents have divided her into a large number of separate political entities".¹

Nizam-ul-Mulk founder of Asafjahi Dynasty ruled Hyderabad State independently from 1724 during later Mughals period. The second ruler of Hyderabad state, Nizam Ali concluded subsidiary Alliance with British Governor General Lord Wellesley in 1798. He was the first Indian King to sign this pact. Nizam supported British during 1857 Revolt and became Faithful Ally to British Government. The Seventh Ruler of Hyderabad state Nizam Mir Usman Ali Khan succeeded to throne on 29th August 1911.

British East India Company started in 1600. From the Battle of Plassey (1757) Company got hold on Bengal and slowly with wars, pacts and strategies it expanded throughout India ruled up to 1857 revolt. After that British Crown directly ruled Indian subjects. At the end of Second World War, the then British Prime Minister Atlee announced to grant Independence to India. The last British Viceroy Lord Mountbatten prepared 3rd June 1947 plan for transfer of power and partition.

Vallabhbhai Patel was born on 31st October 1875 at Nadiad in Gujarat State to Jhaverbhai and Ladbapatel. He completed Barrister course at London and rose as leading lawyer. Vallabhbhai Patel associated with Gandhiji during Kheda Movement. From that onwards Patel transformed to staunch follower of Gandhiji and organized several movements during Freedom struggle. Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel assumed the charge of newly established States Department to negotiate with princely states on 5th July 1947. Patel speed up the process of integration, all the princely states joined in Indian union except Hyderabad, Junagarh and Kashmir.

Methodology:

The primary sources, “For a United India : Speeches of Sardar Patel”, V.P. Menon’s “The Story of the Integration of the Indian States”, K.M. Munshi’s work “The End of an Era; Hyderabad Memories”, “Sardar Patel’s Correspondence”, General J.N. Chaudhari’s work “An Autobiography” and secondary sources, Lion M.G. Agarwal’s work Freedom fighters of India vol.2, Bipanchandra’s work Modern India, Jagadish Saran Sharma’s India since the Advent of the British A Descriptive Chronology works gone through for Literature Review. Here there are some micro level gaps found in the present research paper topic. Thus a little effort put for to fill the gaps in the role of Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel in Integration of Hyderabad State. Chronological method and Historical Method both combined followed in this research paper. Some limitations on contemporary sources lacked, this methods gave boost to limelight the efforts of great leader Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel in Hyderabad episode.

Hyderabad State

There were nearly around 600 princely states hailed in Indian peninsula during British rule. Some are tiny, others are medium size and few are bigger princely states. Among Hyderabad State is one of the biggest princely states includes parts of present day Telangana, Karnataka, Maharashtra and Andhra Pradesh States. It consists 82,000 square miles in area. The population composition of Hyderabad state resembles Mini India. Most of 86% of population belongs to Hindu, 12½% Muslims and remaining 1½% are Christians. But its ruler Nizam was a Muslim. It’s geographical location like a heart of Country. It was a land locked state. Hyderabad state combined with rich resources.

Integration of Princely States into Indian Union:

After two centuries of colonial rule, with various phases of freedom struggle India stood at the doors of freedom on the other side chaos of partition in August 1947. The British Paramountcy is ending in Indian Sub continent on the eve of Independence of two Nations India and Pakistan. It is the time for around 600 princely states to join either in Indian dominion or Pakistan dominion.

Jawaharlal Nehru, addressing All India Committee on June 17th 1947 said “We will not recognise any independence for any state in India. Further any recognition of such independence by any foreign power whichever it may be and wherever it may be, will be considered an unfriendly act”.²

Gandhiji had said to Patel “The problem of the States is so difficult that you alone can solve it” Patel was considered a statesman of integrity with the practical acumen and resolve to accomplish a monumental task.³

Here Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel, who took incharge of States Department played crucial role in integration of princely states in Indian Union. Patel applied various techniques and strategies for this purpose. The Prime Minister of India Jawaharlal Nehru also gave free hand to him in most of occasions. V.P. Menon, trusted advisor of Wavell, Lord Mountbatten and then confidante senior bureaucrat in Patel’s team, played a vital role in the process integration of Princely States.

Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel consulted rulers of princely states and gave assurance for their fame and dignity. Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel said “I have a few words to say the Rulers of Indian States among whom I am happy to count many as

my personal friends. Let not the future generation curse us for having had the opportunity but having failed to turn it to our mutual advantage.....”⁴

Lord Mountbatten explained all the Princes about Instrument of accession. Mahatma Gandhi called the Princes to join the Indian Union. Mostly majority of Princely States signed the Instrument of Accession except Hyderabad, Junagarh and Kashmir.

Integration of Hyderabad State into Indian Union

Hyderabad State was land locked region which was surrounded by Indian Soil. “Flung almost completely across the Indian Peninsula, the great state of Hyderabad holds a strategic position of the first importance both from the Political and Military point of view. In an emergency it could practically isolate the South from the North”.⁵

Though Hyderabad State merger with India was necessary element, the ruler Nizam forgot the interest of his subjects. Nizam issued a Firman that Hyderabad State remains Independent on 11th July 1947. Nizam felt that British Government grant dominion status which was later denied. All types of negotiations for accession of Hyderabad State proved unproductive. With the support of Nizam, Ittehad-ul-Muslimin Party dictate terms and conditions in that State. The Nizam was a simple dress styled Emperor. “He was a modern Croesus with a civil list of 1000 pounds a day and yet he chooses to dress himself like a beggar”.⁶

The Nizam informed the Crown representative that he would watch the relations between India and Pakistan before entering into organic relation with either Dominion. After several consultations with Lord Mountbatten through Nizam’s constitutional advisor Walter Monckton Nizam signed Standstill Agreement with Government of India on 29th November 1947. Mountbatten felt Standstill Agreement “Sanguine that it would allow heads to cool and hearts to soften and that before the expiry of the Agreement the Nizam like all other rulers would accede to India”.⁷

The main aim of Mountbatten and Nehru in avoiding a forced annexation was to prevent an outbreak of Hindu-Muslim violence. Patel insisted that if Hyderabad was allowed to continue with its antics, the prestige of the Government would fall and then neither Hindus nor Muslims would feel secure in its realm.⁸

Meanwhile Razakars, irregular Army played prominent role in Nizam’s Government. The Nizam and his Razakar leaders considered the Standstill Agreement “as providing breathing space in which to secure the withdrawal of the Indian troops of their position and strength to a stage when they would be able to assert the Independence of State”.⁹

Gradually Nizam breached the Standstill Agreement before its ink dry. Razakars leader Kasim Razvi cried “The day is not far off when the waves of the Bay of Bengal will be washing the feet of our Sovereign”.¹⁰

Hyderabad State ruler Nizam also wants to create Third Dominion in Indian Subcontinent. “He dreamt of the Supreme glory of becoming the head of entire Muslim World”.¹¹

Razakars created nuisance and indulged violent activities in Hyderabad State. Even Muslim intellectuals and Moderate leaders had not raised their voice against the violent activities of Razakars. Once, Sir Salar Jung, an important nobleman of Hyderabad told K.M. Munshi “Our lives and properties are at the mercy of Razvi... I have served the state for years..... but all the time I am afraid for my life”.¹²

Rajakars murdered the Imroz News paper Editor Shoibullah Khan. Who published series of Articles against Razakars. Kasim Razvi said “the hand that rises against the Muslim should either drop down or would be cut off”.¹³

The Ministry of States of India informed the Prime Minister of Hyderabad State on specific violations of the Standstill Agreement and aksed for remedial action through its Agent K.M. Munshi, who was also ill treated by Nizam’s Government. Prime Minister of Hyderabad made counter complaints and rebutted charges against Hyderabad. The Ministry of States of India asked for immediate ban on Razakars and to stop of hostile Press and Radio Propaganda.

Mountbatten felt unhappy on the course of events in Hyderabad state during his farewell, Mountbatten said “Munshi I had many jolts in my life. But never have received such a shock as was given me by these people of Hyderabad”.¹⁴

The Nizam notified Indian currency not legal in his State. His Government gave a loan of 200 million rupees to Pakistan. Nizam’s Commander-in-Chief El Edroos visited Europe countries for Military Air Crafts. Some of his officials engaged to procure arms and ammunition. All these secret reports from various sources as well as their official Agent K.M. Munshi reports were watching by Government of India.

In Hyderabad State Standstill Agreement used as breathe space by Razakars to raise their Volunteers and to equip with arms. Razakars attacked several villages, even looted trains. Meanwhile communists organised Night Governments, Razakars played as Day Governments and created chaos in Hyderabad State. Even after these atrocities Nizam appealed to C.Rajagopalachari and Government of India for clarifications of Standstill Agreement. Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel rejected these and said “Settlement has gone to England”.

Nizam’s Government send delegation to refer Hyderabad issue to United Nations Organization headed by Moin Nawaz Jung on 10th September 1948. At the last stage Patel applied Force strategy to solve Hyderabad problem. Sardar Vallbhbhai Patel initiated the Government of India for Military operation in Hyderabad on 13th September 1948. The Indian troops entered from North West and South sides of Hyderabad State. Major General J.N. Chaudhari headed this Military operation and Indian Government coded as “Operation Polo” or Police Action. In these Police Action, thousands of Razakar Militants had been killed, but Hyderabad state integrated into Indian Union with less resistance.

Nizam’s Army under El Edroos surrendered to Indian Army on 17th September 1948. Operation Polo lasted for 108 hours with successful mission removing cancer in the belly of India.

Conclusion:

“There was not a single communal Incident in the whole length and breadth of India throughout the time of operation. There was universal jubilation at the swift and successful ending of Hyderabad episode and message of congratulation poured in to the Government of India from all parts of the country.”¹⁵

Thus Sardar Patel convinced the rulers in different approaches to sign Instrument of accession with Indian Dominion. He appealed to the princes of provinces and their people to take their due and honourable share in the shaping of India. In the short span of period Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel combined with all efforts brought most of the princely states under one Nation.

Sir Walter Monckton gave significant comments about Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel efforts to solve the Hyderabad issue in peaceful path remarks “I want to tell you how relieved I am that the action which you were eventually driven to take did not result in large scale communal troubles. I know how anxious you were not to take the action at all and how hard you struggled to avoid it. I honestly believe that moderate world opinion shared your view rather than the other. Still, however that may be, everyone who wants to see a peaceful and prosperous India will rejoice, as I do that episode is quietly finished”.¹⁶

Thus Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel handled all these issues relating to Hyderabad State in a systematic stern manner and solved the delectated problem into a peaceful end.

Chronological Events that led to Integration of Hyderabad State to India

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| 1724 | - Hyderabad State founded by Nizam-ul-mulk |
| 29 th August 1911 | - Nizam Mir Usman Aikhan of Asafjahi Dynasty succeeded as seventh Ruler. |
| 20 th February 1947 | - British Prime Minister Climent Atlee announced June 1948 as a deadline for transfer of power. |
| 3 rd June 1947 | - Lord Mountbatten announced transfer of power and India’s partition. |
| 5 th July 1947 | - Sardar Valabhabhai Patel took charge “States Department” to deal with States. |
| 11 th July 1947 | - Nizam issued a Firman that Hyderabad would remain Independent when the British Paramountcy lapsed on 15 th August 1947. |
| 15 th August 1947 | - Indian Dominion was born. |
| 29 th November 1947 | - The Nizam and Indian Government signed Standstill Agreement. |
| 23 rd March 1948 | - The Ministry of States of India informed Hyderabad State on the specific violation of Standstill Agreement. |
| 15 th April 1948 | - Diwan of Hyderabad made counter complaints against India. |
| 15 th May 1948 | - The Ministry of States of India asked immediate ban of Razakar and to stop hostile press propaganda against India by Hyderabad State. |
| 20 th June 1948 | - Nehru gave farewell to Lord Mountbatten. |
| 9 th September 1948 | - M.A. Jinnah passed away. |
| 10 th September 1948 | - Nizam send delegation to UNO headed by Moin Nawab Jung. |
| 13 th to 17 th Sept. 1948 | - Government of India launched Police Action against Hyderabad State. |
| 17 th September 1948 | - Nizam’s Army surrendered to Indian Army. |
| 22 nd September 1948 | - Nizam withdraw the complaint made to UNO. |

Asafjhazi Dynasty – Rulers of Hyderabad State

1)	Nizam-ul-mulk	-	1724-1748
	↓		
	a) Nasir Jang	-	1748-1750
	↓		
	b) Salabat Jang	-	1751-1760
	↓		
2)	Nizam Ali	-	1760-1803
	↓		
3)	SikindarJah	-	1803-1829
	↓		
4)	Nasir-ud-daulah	-	1829-1857
	↓		
5)	Afzul-ud-daulah	-	1857-1869
	↓		
6)	Mahabub Alikhan	-	1869-1911
	↓		
7)	Usman Alikhan	-	1911-1948

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